

High-voltage circuit breaker condition-dependent failure rate with covariates

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Key Words: Asset management, Condition-monitoring, Health index, High-voltage circuit breaker, Risk assessment.

SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

High-voltage circuit breakers (HVCBs) are essential protection devices which should also be included in power system reliability analysis. When using Monte-Carlo simulation methods the reliability of individual components is incorporated into the analysis through sampling failure events. Therefore, methods for attaining an HVCB failure rate are investigated. Furthermore, the failure rate is dependent on the condition of the HVCB therefore we are interested in creating a condition-dependent failure rate.

A case study is presented with statistics on HVCB outages from the Icelandic transmission system. Exponential and Weibull models are fitted to the HVCB uptime vs event data, where the events include both planned and unplanned outages. The data was split into a training and testing data set to see which model fits the best. The Brier score indicated that the Exponential fit was the best model to describe HVCB time-to-event (TTE). Survival analysis techniques were used to investigate the effect of covariates on the failure rate. Specifically, the Cox Proportional hazards Model (PHM) was used to extract a baseline failure rate from the data. Then an HVCB health index was used in place of the covariates and regression parameters in the Cox PHM equation to generate a condition-dependent failure rate.

Finally, the condition-dependent failure rate measurements were calibrated using the results of the best fitted model to the historical data.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

The future energy system calls for increased electrification [1] thereby making society more dependent on the reliable and efficient operation of the power system. Asset management strategies [2] are transitioning from time-based to condition-based to enable maintenance optimization [3]. Condition monitoring techniques have improved the ability to conduct

failure prognostics [4]. High-voltage circuit breakers (HVCBs) are prevalent in the power system and are critical devices for ensuring the reliability of the system [5]. There are also associated condition-monitoring techniques available for failure prognostics and health index calculation for HVCBs.

In previous work, a health index model for HVCBs was developed [6]. Condition data was used as input into the model and a corresponding health index was computed based on the detection of failure mechanisms. However, the HVCB health index model did not consider covariates such as voltage, manufacturer, or age. Furthermore, in power system reliability analysis failure rates are used to model the probability of failure for individual components and not health indices [7]. Therefore, methods will be investigated to translate an HVCB health index into an equivalent failure rate. The failure rate based on the health index which is in turn based on condition data is referred to as a condition-dependent failure rate [8]. This allows for more accurate power system reliability analysis than the traditional approach using a single, constant, average failure rate for HVCBs that does not consider their condition. A condition-dependent failure rate is also a useful metric when conducting risk-based asset management. Statistical methods which utilize data from failure databases as in [9] and calculate an apparent age have been used for transformers but with the practice of preventive retirement, the end-of-life failure statistics can be right-censored thereby lacking sufficient data. Therefore, additional novel methods will be investigated, which instead of making use of information from a failure database of scrapped components, can utilize information from an outage database related to both planned and unplanned outages to help translate the HVCB health index into an equivalent failure rate.

The risk of an event such as an HVCB failure is the combination of the consequence of the event and the probability that the event will occur. Determining the consequence of an HVCB failure event is achievable through commonly used methods but quantifying the probability is made more problematic due to the practice of preventive retirement [10]. Therefore, methods are needed to quantify the probability of

failure in the face of these challenges.

The probability of failure is not a constant but can be described by a certain probability distribution $f(t)$ of the time-to-failure which depends on the component being characterized. In reliability terminology, the integral of $f(t)$ is known as the cumulative failure distribution $Q(t)$ and the complement is known as the reliability function or survival function denoted by $R(t)$ as shown in Equation (1). A transition rate is used to reflect the probability of failure. A transition rate is the probability that an event will occur in an infinitesimally small-time interval. When the event is a failure event the transition rate is called a hazard rate or failure rate denoted by λ and calculated as per Equation (2).

$$R(t) = 1 - Q(t) \quad (1)$$

$$\lambda(t) = \frac{f(t)}{R(t)} \quad (2)$$

The research question that this paper aims to address is how we can incorporate the condition of HVCBs into system-level analysis. The first step in this process is to create a health index from condition monitoring data, which was accomplished using a framework based on failure modes, effects, and criticality analysis (FMECA). The next step and the objective of this study is to investigate the use of survival analysis techniques to convert the health index into a failure rate which can be used in system-level analysis.

1.2 Related work

Reference [11] described the use of statistical and estimation techniques in quantifying a probability of failure for power transformers. Statistical methods included Weibull analysis and accelerated failure time models, but due to a lack of data related to age and probability of failure more sophisticated methods were needed. Estimation techniques included the adjustment of the failure rate using a relative probability of failure but again this method's accuracy was dependent on a large amount of failure data from a similar component. The failure probability vs apparent age method was also described. This is where a probability of failure vs age curve is constructed using data related to failures in service and condition-based preventive retirements. Then component condition data is analyzed and matched to this curve to indicate an apparent age with an associated probability of failure.

Reference [9] used the apparent age methodology for determining the probability of failure for power transformers by analyzing a database with information on scrapped transformers. Reference [12] proposed a methodology where a condition-dependent failure rate for transformers could be computed which also accounts for preventive retirement.

Existing research suffers from limitations related to the need to access a failure database. Failure databases can have a low amount of data due to the long life of components, the practice of preventive retirement and the need to carry out a failure analysis. This research aims to overcome this limitation by making use of information from an outage database. Outage databases are logged on the system-level so data is often available. Existing research is also limited concerning how external factors other than the condition monitoring data affect

the failure rate of a component. This research plans to overcome this limitation by making use of survival analysis techniques that can account for the effect of covariates. Finally, there is a void of literature related to HVCB condition-dependent failure rates and associated techniques. This research will fill this gap by proposing a methodology and exemplifying it using real data in a case study.

1.3 Cox proportional hazards model

The Cox proportional hazards model (PHM) estimates the effects of different covariates on the failure rate. The failure rate is assumed to be the product of a baseline failure rate and a scaling factor as shown in Equation (3). The baseline failure rate $\lambda_0(t)$ is a function of time and the scaling factor $e^{(z\beta)}$ is a function of the covariates z and regression parameters β . The scaling factor has an exponential response to the covariates and regression parameters. The regression parameters can be seen as weighting factors representing the effects of the covariates [13].

$$\lambda(t, z) = \lambda_0(t)e^{(z\beta)} \quad (3)$$

The use of the proportional hazards model allows us to represent survival not only as a function of time but of specific covariates. The scaling factor is related to the failure rate by a multiple of the baseline failure rate. The covariates that influence HVCB survival can be continuous or binary (or categorical variables). Continuous covariates such as temperature or age can vary and take on many values. A categorical covariate such as manufacturer can only take on a limited set of values and needs to be specifically declared.

1.4 Outline and contributions

The scope of the paper was introduced in section 1. Section 2 will present the proposed methodology with a case study presented in section 3. Finally, conclusions will be made in section 4.

The contributions of the paper are:

1. Methodology for the creation of an HVCB condition-dependent failure rate from a health index using the Cox PHM.
2. Analysis of HVCB survival times and failure rates.
3. Calibration of computed condition-dependent failure rates to historical data.
4. Proposed method based on the use of outage data rather than failure data to generate a failure rate.

2 METHODOLOGY

The methodology to compute a condition-dependent failure rate is illustrated in Figure 1. The outage database that we had access to contained information related to the HVCBs age, number of outages and downtime. No data was available on exactly when the outages occurred. Therefore, when the event flag was 1 (occurrence of an event) the data was deemed to be interval-censored and when the event flag was 0 the data was deemed to be right censored.

Figure 1: Condition-dependent failure rate framework

The uptime is calculated by the age minus the downtime. If an event occurred, the data is interval-censored and the lower-bound is equal to 0 and the upper-bound is equal to the uptime since the event could have occurred anywhere within this interval. If no event occurred during the observation period, the data is right censored and the lower bound is equal to the uptime and the upper bound is equal to infinity.

An approach from reference [14] is then adopted to convert the interval-censored data into right-censored data. This is due to the issues encountered getting the Cox PHM to converge when using interval-censored data. Different approaches to imputation were investigated but to simplify things we set the duration equal to half the upper-bound when converting the event interval-censored data into right-censored data. For the non-event right-censored data we set the duration equal to the lower bound.

The Cox proportional hazards model is used to extract a baseline failure rate from the historical outage data, removing the effects of the covariates. The more covariates that are added into the model the better we can get an approximation of the baseline failure rate. Equation (3) can be expanded to Equation (4) when considering multiple covariates.

Our assumption is that the sum of the products of the covariates and regression parameters acts as a health index, which is a normalized value of the products of scores and weights. Therefore, by using the Cox PHM to extract the baseline failure rate and substituting the health index in place of the covariates and regression parameters, we propose the use of Equation (5) to calculate a condition-dependent failure rate (CDFR). In Equation (5) the average of $\lambda_0(t)$ is taken producing an average baseline failure rate λ_0 which is a constant. This simplification is justified by the demonstration in Sec. 3 that the failure rate in this case study does not have a significant time dependence.

The benefit of using a health index instead of the covariates and regression parameters is that the health index is based on actual measurements that quantify the technical condition of an individual component and not long-term averages from historical data for a fleet of components like the covariates and regression parameters are. Using a health index allows us to utilize condition-monitoring measurements that reflect the present condition of a component.

$$\lambda(t, z) = \lambda_0(t) e^{\sum_{j=1}^q z_j \beta_j} \quad (4)$$

$$\lambda(HI) = \lambda_0 e^{(1-HI)} \quad (5)$$

The HVCB health index model was conceptualized in previous work but further developed into a Python script that calculates a health index from condition data. The condition data analyzed were the trip coil current (TCC) measurements [15]. The framework for the developed HVCB health index model is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: HVCB health index model

The health index model has five main sections. The first section imports the condition monitoring data and results from the failure modes, effects, and criticality analysis. The second section extracts the features from the condition monitoring data. The approach used in this model smooths the condition data to remove noise. The features are then detected by applying a derivative to the data and extracting the extremum points. The window size of the moving average filter is refined to extract the features. A small window size preserves the features but does not filter much noise. A large window size filters the noise but does not preserve the features as well. Therefore, a trade-off must be made. The third section contains validation rules to quality control the feature extraction process and invalidate any measurements where the features could not be properly extracted. The fourth section puts the features through an expert judgement-scoring system. The final section takes the expert judgement score and risk prioritization number from the

FMECA which works as a justified weighting factor for each failure mechanism in the health index model to create a health index. The health index is then used in the methodology of this paper.

The final step of the methodology of Figure 1 is to calibrate the condition-dependent failure rates. Historical data is used to calibrate the condition-dependent failure rates using Equation (6). An approach from [16] is adopted to calibrate the mean calculated failure rate with the mean historical failure rate. This is achieved by multiplying the failure rate obtained using Equation (5) by the calibration coefficient (CC) obtained in Equation (6).

$$CC = \frac{\text{Mean historical failure rate}}{\text{Mean calculated failure rate}} \quad (6)$$

3 CASE STUDY

A case study was carried out using information from an outage database from the Icelandic transmission system of 466 HVCBs, where 216 of them experienced a failure in their lifetime and 250 were right-censored.

To give an overview of the data set, a histogram of the HVCB outage times is shown in Figure 3. It shows that most outages last for less than a day with a few rare events having outage durations of up to 105 days.

Figure 3: Histogram of HVCB outage times

Figure 3 shows the distribution of outage times, but transmission system operators (TSOs) are also interested in survival times, failure rates and the factors that influence the failure rate. Therefore, the methodology shown in Figure 1 was followed for the data set and performed with the following covariates:

- Voltage.
- Manufacturer.
- Age.
- Substation.

However, when using too many covariates at once convergence issues were experienced. Therefore, the analysis was performed with one covariate at a time. The manufacturer covariate has sensitive information regarding relative failure rates, the substation covariate may not be of interest to the general reader for Icelandic substations and age is not a covariate that is

directly linked to condition. Hence, voltage will be shown as the covariate of interest in this paper. The voltage level categories were 11kV, 33kV, 66kV, 132kV and 220kV.

The lifelines library [17] in Python was used to perform the analysis. When using the voltage level as a covariate in the Cox PHM the extracted average baseline failure rate was low at 0.004 failures per year (f/yr) compared to the average historical condition-dependent failure rate of 0.033 f/yr. This is because the baseline failure rate is the resulting uncalibrated failure rate when the effects of the covariates are omitted.

Equation (5) was used with the calculated baseline failure rate to translate each of the 83 health indices obtained in a previous study [6] using the methodology depicted in Figure 2 into a condition-dependent failure rate. A plot of how the condition-dependent failure rate varies with health index is illustrated in Figure 4, which also shows where the 83 health indices fall on the theoretical curve of Equation (5).

The 70 HVCB condition-monitoring data points that passed the validation step of Figure 2 have health indices that lie in the range of 100% to 53% since the TCC data accounts for 47% of the failure mechanisms. The 13 HVCB condition-monitoring data points that did not pass the validation step in Figure 2 were given a health index of zero and were assigned the highest failure rate.

Figure 4: Condition-dependent failure rate

Calibration is required to match the average calculated failure rates with average historical failure rates. To do this a calibration coefficient was calculated using Equation (6).

To investigate the mean historical failure rate both an Exponential and a Weibull model were fitted to the HVCB uptime vs event data, where the uptime consisted of a lower and an upper bound.

An exponential distribution as shown in Equation (7) was fitted to the data with its parameter $\theta = 29.98$ years, which represents a mean time-to-event (TTE) of 29.98 years. The resulting survival function and failure rates are shown in Figure 5. The survival function for an exponential distribution is characterized by Equation (8) and represents the proportion of the population still alive at time t [18]. The median survival time can be found when the survival function is evaluated at 0.5. The exponential model shows a median survival time of 20.78 years. The failure rate of an exponential distribution is

constant and is calculated by Equation (9), which for this model was 0.033 f/yr.

Figure 5: Exponential fit to historical data

$$f(t; \theta) = \frac{1}{\theta} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\theta}\right)} \quad (7)$$

$$R(t; \theta) = 1 - Q(t) = e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\theta}\right)} \quad (8)$$

$$\lambda(t; \theta) = \frac{f(t)}{R(t)} = \frac{1}{\theta} \quad (9)$$

A Weibull distribution as shown in Equation (10) was fitted to the data with its parameters $\eta = 29.24$ years and $\rho = 1.17$. The scale parameter η represents the age at which 63.2% of the population have experienced an event. The shape parameter ρ represents whether the failure rate is decreasing, constant or increasing. When ρ is less than 1 the failure rate is decreasing, when ρ is equal to 1 we have a constant failure rate (exponential distribution) and when ρ is greater than 1 we have an increasing failure rate [19]. Since the shape parameter ρ was close to 1 (95% confidence interval 0.93 to 1.41), this may signify that the TSO has an adequate strategy related to maintenance and preventive retirement that is able to prevent component deterioration which would lead to increasing failure rates. The resulting survival function and failure rates are shown in Figure 6. The survival function for a Weibull distribution is characterized by Equation (11). The median survival time was 21.39 years. The average failure rate can be calculated by Equation (12), which for this model was 0.039 f/yr.

Figure 6: Weibull fit to historical data

$$f(t; \eta, \rho) = \frac{\rho}{\eta} \left(\frac{t}{\eta}\right)^{\rho-1} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\eta}\right)^\rho} \quad (10)$$

$$R(t; \eta, \rho) = 1 - Q(t) = e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\eta}\right)^\rho} \quad (11)$$

$$\lambda(t; \eta, \rho) = \frac{f(t)}{R(t)} = \frac{\rho}{\eta} \left(\frac{t}{\eta}\right)^{\rho-1} \quad (12)$$

To test which model had the best fit the data was split into a training data set and a testing data set. When a model is trained on one data set and its predictive performance is tested on

another data set that the model has not seen this enables an unbiased evaluation of the model. The model was then trained on the training data set and tested against the testing data set. To quantify which model had the best fit the Brier Score was used as shown in Equation (13), where f_t represents the model prediction at time t , O_t represents the actual outcome at time t and N represents the number of observations. The exponential model had a Brier Score of 0.262 and the Weibull model had a Brier score of 0.289. A lower Brier score represents a better fit, so the exponential model fitted the data set the best. [20]

$$BS = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N (f_t - O_t)^2 \quad (13)$$

The condition-dependent failure rates from Equation (5) were then multiplied by the CC parameter in Equation (6) to produce the calibrated results as shown in Figure 7. These failure rates can be sampled into system-level analysis for individual components instead of the single, constant failure rate used in traditional methods.

Figure 7: Calibrated condition-dependent failure rates

4 CONCLUSIONS

A framework for converting a health index into a condition-dependent failure rate was presented for HVCBs. The framework was based on the use of the Cox proportional hazards model, which filtered out a baseline failure rate by removing the effects of covariates.

A health index was used in place of the covariates and regression parameters to calculate a condition-dependent failure rate. Then the condition-dependent failure rate was calibrated to historical records, where the historical data for HVCB survival times were best modelled by an exponential distribution.

Failure rate estimation and thus asset management could be improved if all events related to an individual asset were tracked systematically. In this study, time stamps on exactly when outages occurred rather than just a flag that an outage had occurred would have improved the accuracy of the failure rate model. This is because time stamps would have eliminated the need to handle interval-censored data.

Future work will focus on how the condition-dependent failure rate can be incorporated into system-level analysis,

which estimates the reliability of electricity supply for a power system that contains multiple HVCBs with different technical condition.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was funded in part by the Research Council of Norway under Grant 308781 (“VulPro”) and in part by Statnett, and Landsnet. The authors thank all VulPro project partners for useful discussions.

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